

Unification of treatments and interventions for tinnitus patients

Proposal No.: 848261

Deliverable D8.3: Sustainability and business plan

Deliverable No. D24 – WP8

Authors	Ilias Trochidis (VIL), Winfried Schlee (UHREG)
Responsible of Deliverable	VIL
Target Dissemination Level	Public
Status of the Document	Version 2.0

Table of contents

List of Figures	3
List of Tables.....	3
List of changes.....	4
1 Introduction and Methodology	5
1.1 Exploitation and sustainability in UNITI.....	5
1.2 Purpose and scope	5
1.3 Methodology.....	6
2 UNITI Exploitable results	6
2.1 UNITI CDSS.....	8
2.2 UNITI mobile application	13
2.3 UNITI Randomised Clinical Trials	16
2.4 UNITI Genetics.....	18
2.5 Socio-economic impact of tinnitus.....	19
2.6 UNITI data.....	20
2.7 Further important technical outcomes.....	21
2.7.1 A Contextual Multi-armed Bandit Method to Develop Patient-Centric Prediction Models 21	
2.7.2 Interactive System for Similarity-Based Inspection and Assessment of the Well-Being of mHealth Users.....	22
2.7.3 COBALT – a cost-aware method for the discovery of predictive subgroups.....	23
2.7.4 Neighbourhood based methods for predictions on sparse mHealth data	24
2.8 Assessment of UNITI outputs/innovations	25
3 Intellectual Property Rights.....	26
4 UNITI business models.....	29
4.1 UNITI CDSS business model.....	30
4.2 UNITI mobile app business model	33
5 Commercialization and business plan	35
6 Summary of exploitation actions implemented	37

6.1	UNITI Publications	37
6.2	UNITI project website	37
6.3	Exploitation results and achievements	38
7	Partners' exploitation activities and impact	39
8	UNITI working group	42
9	Conclusions	44
	Appendix I: UNITI Socioeconomic survey (updated version)	45

List of Figures

Figure 1: UNITI Clinical Decision Support System	9
Figure 2: UNITI mobile app (iOS and Android)	14
Figure 3: UNITI data	20
Figure 4: A Contextual Multi-armed Bandit Method to Develop Patient-Centric Prediction Models	22
Figure 5: Interactive System for Similarity-Based Inspection and Assessment of the Well-Being of mHealth Users	23
Figure 6: COBALT – a cost-aware method for the discovery of predictive subgroups	24
Figure 7: Neighbourhood based methods for predictions on sparse mHealth data	25
Figure 9: Timeline for important WG activities	44

List of Tables

Table 1: Analysis of the IPRs involved in UNITI outcomes	28
--	----

List of changes

- Added **Section 4** Business models
- Added **Section 5** Commercialization and business plan
- Minor edits and updates in Section 3 Intellectual Property Rights
- Minor edits and updates in Section 9 Conclusions
- Reordering of project outputs in Section 2 UNITI project outputs

1 Introduction and Methodology

1.1 Exploitation and sustainability in UNITI

The UNITI exploitation plan sets up the environment for the successful exploitation, sustainability and commercialization of UNITI outputs. The main aim of exploitation, sustainability and business plan in UNITI was to bring all the UNITI innovative results and outputs to key stakeholders, to successfully transfer UNITI know-how and technologies and to identify commercialization opportunities for the UNITI results.

This report presents the most important UNITI outputs (**UNITI Key Exploitable Results**) and the most important dissemination and exploitation actions that UNITI consortium has carried out. For the results that have commercialization potential (UNITI CDSS and UNITI mobile app), the consortium developed their business models and developed a plan for actions that need to be implemented after the end of the project towards increasing their business potential.

In brief, the most important Dissemination and Exploitation actions in UNITI were the number of **scientific publications** to high impact factor journals and conferences, and the fact the most of the UNITI data and tools will be **open** for researchers to further analyse them. Transparency and openness were the two main principles of UNITI exploitation. For UNITI CDSS and UNITI mobile app, the consortium developed business models and a plan on actions that the consortium is committed to implement after the end of the project. For the sustainability of UNITI results we propose the development of the **UNITI working group** that will continue working in the research areas of UNITI and will aim to exploit and identify commercialization opportunities for the main UNITI results.

1.2 Purpose and scope

The report is the main outcome of “Task 8.2 Exploitation, Sustainability & Business Plans” and aims to:

- Present the key **UNITI exploitable results** focusing on the exploitation actions implemented for each result.
- Identify the UNITI results with **commercialization potential** and present their business models.
- Define the **sustainability plan** that the consortium will follow to sustain the project outputs, beyond the end of the project.

1.3 Methodology

The methodology used to realize the project's exploitation potential consisted of the following phases:

- UNITI exploitation exploration / innovation management (M1 – M10)
- UNITI exploitation experimentation (M11 – M30)
- UNITI exploitation implementation (M31 – M45)

The aim of the **exploration phase** was to identify the main UNITI innovations (key exploitable results), to assess these innovations with regards to their exploitation potential and to inform the UNITI consortium about their contractual obligations to disseminate and exploit the innovative research results of the project.

The aim of the **experimentation phase** was to set the environment for the dissemination and exploitation of the important UNITI research outputs and for the identification of the outputs that have commercialization potential. For these outcomes the value propositions were defined, and appropriate business and sustainability models were developed.

The aim of the **implementation phase** was to present the individual and co-operative exploitation plans of UNITI project partners. It also presents a plan for actions to ensure the sustainability of the project outcomes (tools, methods and research) after the end of the project.

2 UNITI Exploitable results

In this section we present the key exploitable results of UNITI project. These are the projects' results that have been developed within the project's lifetime and have exploitation potential. During the 45 months of the project, UNITI consortium worked hard to develop tangible results (even beyond the project's objectives) that aimed to assist the tinnitus research community develop novel treatments for all types of tinnitus so that relief can be obtained by everyone who suffers from it.

The most important exploitable results of UNITI are the following:

- **UNITI Clinical Decision Support System (CDSS):** A Clinical Decision Support System has been developed (2 cores) using the data from UNITI Randomized Clinical Trials (RCTs).
- **UNITI mobile app:** a mobile framework available under iOS and Android which goal is the treatment of chronic tinnitus patients. Patients will receive a module for

psychoeducation, a module for sound stimulation and a module for the daily assessment of tinnitus (tinnitus diary).

- **UNITI RCTs:** a multicenter, parallel-arm, randomized clinical trial involving patients with chronic subjective tinnitus was conducted.
- **UNITI Genetics:** UNITI combined data from genetics and protein analysis with clinical research to improve diagnosis, prognosis and selection of personalized therapy in chronic tinnitus patients. The discovery of the genetic contribution to tinnitus is a major scientific challenge that UNITI investigated.
- **Socioeconomic impact of tinnitus:** Identifying the economic burden of tinnitus in various cost categories is crucial to better understand tinnitus healthcare organization and treatment implementability in current practice in various countries and consequently reduce unnecessary costly and ineffective treatment strategies for patients and healthcare systems.
- **UNITI data:** Many types of data have been collected during the project and are available e.g. questionnaire data from the RCTs, UNITI mobile app data, blood data, laboratory tests, hearing aid data, data from the socio-economic survey, UNITI big online study.

Together with the core results, UNITI consortium produced a number of important technical outputs that are worth mentioning since they are considered to have exploitation and sustainability potential. These technical outcomes are the following:

- **A Contextual Multi-armed Bandit Method to Develop Patient-Centric Prediction Models:** a method that monitors patients who interact with an mHealth app and finds a good balance between predictors that see only a single patient's data, those that see the patient's neighborhood, and the global model trained on all patients.
- **Interactive System for Similarity-Based Inspection and Assessment of the Well-Being of mHealth Users:** The method showcases a GUI web application that assists the clinician in inspecting the symptom progression of, and in visualising the short-term predictions for a patient's disease progression.
- **COBALT – a cost-aware method for the discovery of predictive subgroups:** COBALT is trained to predict the outcome of each candidate treatment while minimizing the amount of information that needs to be recorded before treatment.
- **Neighbourhood based methods for predictions on sparse mHealth data:** a method that finds for each user those users whose data can improve prediction. The method

collects data iteratively, and identifies users who enhance the predictors of many other users.

A more detailed description of each UNITI result is presented in the following sub-sections along with the exploitation goals that were achieved and the plan for the next steps after the end of the project.

2.1 UNITI CDSS

UNITI CDSS suggests the optimal treatment strategy for a tinnitus patient based on a set of heterogeneous data. It can determine the suitability and expected attachment of a particular patient to a list of available clinical interventions, utilizing predictive and classification machine learning models. During the development process various algorithms were tested to model the CDSS' prediction and their categorisation and consequently integration was based in their R2 scores.

CDSS are always data driven and the goal in the field of tinnitus is to integrate as many and as diverse data as possible to optimally describe / model tinnitus and offer predictions for personalised treatment.

Genetics have been already incorporated as well as electrophysiological data (ABRs, AMLRs) and analysis has been performed and published. UNITI CDSS is still lacking medical imaging data (MRIs, f-MRIs) as well as EEG and MEG graphs. Bridging our results to basic research might also require the introduction of animal models with tinnitus predisposition into the analysis regime.

Participation in future research projects in the field of tinnitus will enhance the generation of new data and the continuation of this research.

Figure 1: UNITI Clinical Decision Support System

Exploitation achievements

Business model: A business model has been developed by the UNITI consortium for the UNITI CDSS. The business model is presented in Section 4.1.

Scientific publications: With regards to dissemination and exploitation achievements, several scientific publications focused on presenting the status and results of the development of UNITI CDSS:

- Schlee, W., Langguth, B., Pryss, R., Allgaier, J., Mulansky, L., Vogel, C., Spiliopoulou, M., Schleicher, M., Unnikrishnan, V., Puga, C., Manta, O., Sarafidis, M., Kouris, I., Vellidou, E., Koutsouris, D., Koloutsou, K., Spanoudakis, G., Cederroth, C., & Kikidis, D. (2021). Using Big Data to Develop a Clinical Decision Support System for Tinnitus Treatment. *Current topics in behavioral neurosciences*, 10.1007/7854_2021_229. Advance online publication. https://doi.org/10.1007/7854_2021_229.
- Kikidis, D., Vassou, E., Schlee, W., Iliadou, E., Markatos, N., Triantafyllou, A., & Langguth, B. (2021). Methodological Aspects of Randomized Controlled Trials for Tinnitus: A Systematic Review and How a Decision Support System Could Overcome Barriers. *Journal of clinical medicine*, 10(8), 1737. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jcm10081737>.
- Bromis, K., Sarafidis, M., Manta, O., Kouris, I., Vellidou, E., Schlee, W., & Koutsouris, D. (2022, July). Predicting the optimal therapeutic intervention for tinnitus patients using random forest regression: A preliminary study of UNITI's decision support system model. In 2022 44th Annual International Conference of the IEEE Engineering in

- Medicine & Biology Society (EMBC) (pp. 2655-2658). IEEE.
<https://doi.org/10.1109/embc48229.2022.9871331>
- Manta, O., Sarafidis, M., Schlee, W., Consoulas, C., Kikidis, D., & Koutsouris, D. (2022, July). Electrophysiological differences in distinct hearing threshold level individuals with and without tinnitus distress. In 2022 44th Annual International Conference of the IEEE Engineering in Medicine & Biology Society (EMBC) (pp. 1630-1633). IEEE.
<https://doi.org/10.1109/embc48229.2022.9871392>
 - Puga, C., Niemann, U., Schlee, W., & Spiliopoulou, M. (2023). A cost-based multi-layer network approach for the discovery of patient phenotypes. *International Journal of Data Science and Analytics*, 1-21. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2209.09032>
 - Shahania, S., Unnikrishnan, V., Pryss, R., Kraft, R., Schobel, J., Hannemann, R., ... & Spiliopoulou, M. (2022). Predicting Ecological Momentary Assessments in an App for Tinnitus by Learning From Each User's Stream With a Contextual Multi-Armed Bandit. *Frontiers in neuroscience*, 16.
 - Prakash S, Unnikrishnan V, Pryss R, Kraft R, Schobel J, Hannemann R, Langguth B, Schlee W, Spiliopoulou M. (2021) Interactive System for Similarity-Based Inspection and Assessment of the Well-Being of mHealth Users. *Entropy*. 2021; 23(12):1695. <https://doi.org/10.3390/e23121695>
 - Puga, C., Niemann, U., Unnikrishnan, V., Schleicher, M., Schlee, W., & Spiliopoulou, M. (2021, October). Discovery of Patient Phenotypes through Multi-layer Network Analysis on the Example of Tinnitus. In 2021 IEEE 8th International Conference on Data Science and Advanced Analytics (DSAA) (pp. 1-10). IEEE.
 - Schleicher, M., Unnikrishnan, V., Neff, P., Simoes, J., Probst, T., Pryss, R., Schlee, W. & Spiliopoulou, M. (2020). Understanding adherence to the recording of ecological momentary assessments in the example of tinnitus monitoring. *Scientific Reports*, 10, 22459 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-020-79527-0>.
 - Unnikrishnan, V., Schleicher, M., Shah, Y., Jamaludeen, N., Pryss, R., Schobel, J., Kraft, R., Schlee, W., & Spiliopoulou, M. (2020). The Effect of Non-Personalised Tips on the Continued Use of Self-Monitoring mHealth Applications. *Brain sciences*, 10(12), 924. <https://doi.org/10.3390/brainsci10120924>.
 - Niemann, U., Brueggemann, P., Boecking, B., Mebus, W., Rose, M., Spiliopoulou, M., & Mazurek, B. (2020). Phenotyping chronic tinnitus patients using self-report questionnaire data: Cluster analysis and visual comparison. *Scientific reports*, 10(1), 1-10. ISO 690. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-020-73402-8>.

- Niemann, U., Boecking, B., Brueggemann, P., Mazurek, B., & Spiliopoulou, M. (2020). Gender-Specific Differences in Patients With Chronic Tinnitus-Baseline Characteristics and Treatment Effects. *Frontiers in neuroscience*, 14, 487. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnins.2020.00487>.
- Niemann U, Brueggemann P, Boecking B, Mazurek B, Spiliopoulou M. (2020) Development and internal validation of a depression severity prediction model for tinnitus patients based on questionnaire responses and socio-demographics. *Scientific reports*. 2020 Mar 13;10(1):1-9. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-020-61593-z>.
- Niemann U, Boecking B, Brueggemann P, Mebus W, Mazurek B, Spiliopoulou M. (2020) Tinnitus related distress after multimodal treatment can be characterized using a key subset of baseline variables. *PLoS One*. 2020 Jan 30;15(1):e0228037. PMID: 31999776; PMCID: PMC6991951. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0228037>.
- Schleicher, M., Unnikrishnan, V., Pryss, R., Schobel, J., Schlee, W., & Spiliopoulou, M. (2023). Prediction meets time series with gaps: User clusters with specific usage behavior patterns. *Artificial Intelligence in Medicine*, 142, 102575. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.artmed.2023.102575>.
- Unnikrishnan, V., Schleicher, M., Puga, C., Pryss, R., Vogel, C., Schlee, W., & Spiliopoulou, M. (2023, April). A Similarity-Guided Framework for Error-Driven Discovery of Patient Neighbourhoods in EMA Data. In *Advances in Intelligent Data Analysis XXI: 21st International Symposium on Intelligent Data Analysis, IDA 2023, Louvain-la-Neuve, Belgium, April 12–14, 2023, Proceedings* (pp. 459-471). Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-30047-9_36.
- Schleicher, M., Hamacher, S., Naujoks, M., Günther, K., Schmidt, T., Pryss, R., ... & Spiliopoulou, M. (2022, July). Prediction of declining engagement to self-monitoring apps on the example of tinnitus mHealth data. In *2022 IEEE 35th International Symposium on Computer-Based Medical Systems (CBMS)* (pp. 228-233). IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/CBMS55023.2022.00047>
- Schleicher, M., Pryss, R., Schobel, J., Schlee, W., & Spiliopoulou, M. (2022, October). Expect the gap: A recommender approach to estimate the absenteeism of self-monitoring mHealth app users. In *2022 IEEE 9th International Conference on Data Science and Advanced Analytics (DSAA)* (pp. 1-10). IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109%2fDSAA54385.2022.10032390>.
- Schleicher, M., Pryss, R., Schlee, W., & Spiliopoulou, M. (2022, June). When can I expect the mHealth user to return? Prediction meets time series with gaps. In

International Conference on Artificial Intelligence in Medicine (pp. 310-320). Cham: Springer International Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.artmed.2023.102575>.

- Shahania, S., Unnikrishnan, V., Pryss, R., Kraft, R., Schobel, J., Hannemann, R., Schlee, W., & Spiliopoulou, M. (2021, June). User-centric vs whole-stream learning for EMA prediction. In 2021 IEEE 34th International Symposium on Computer-Based Medical Systems (CBMS) (pp. 307-312). IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/CBMS52027.2021.00033>.
- Unnikrishnan, V., Shah, Y., Schleicher, M., Fernández-Viadero, C., Strandzheva, M., Velikova, D., Schlee, W., & Spiliopoulou, M. (2021, June). Love thy Neighbours: A Framework for Error-Driven Discovery of Useful Neighbourhoods for One-Step Forecasts on EMA data. In 2021 IEEE 34th International Symposium on Computer-Based Medical Systems (CBMS) (pp. 295-300). IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/CBMS52027.2021.00080>.
- Jamaludeen, N., Unnikrishnan, V., Pryss, R., Schobel, J., Schlee, W., & Spiliopoulou, M. (2021, June). Circadian Conditional Granger Causalities on Ecological Momentary Assessment Data from an mHealth App. In 2021 IEEE 34th International Symposium on Computer-Based Medical Systems (CBMS) (pp. 354-359). IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/CBMS52027.2021.00110>.

PhD Thesis: Another significant exploitation result is two PhD thesis that were defended.

- Manta, O. (2023). Development of intelligent machine learning models using multidimensional data for the evaluation and classification of chronic tinnitus patients. <http://dx.doi.org/10.12681/eadd/53670>
- Niemann, U. (2021). Intelligent assistance for expert-driven subpopulation discovery in high-dimensional timestamped medical data. <http://dx.doi.org/10.25673/37453>

Events: During the project period, the UNITI CDSS was presented to a number of events. The most important are the following:

- 43rd Annual International Conference of the IEEE Engineering in Medicine & Biology Society (EMBC) (<https://embc.embs.org/2021/>)
- 44th Annual International Conference of the IEEE Engineering in Medicine & Biology Society (EMBC) (<https://embc.embs.org/2022/>)
- Tinnitus Research Initiative (TRI) conference (<https://www.lab-clint.org/tri2023/>)

- Advances in Intelligent Data Analysis XXI: 21st International Symposium on Intelligent Data Analysis, IDA 2023, Louvain-la-Neuve, Belgium, April 12–14 (<https://ida2023.org>).
- IEEE 35th International Symposium on Computer-Based Medical Systems (CBMS) (<https://2022.cbms-conference.org/>).
- 2022 IEEE 9th International Conference on Data Science and Advanced Analytics (DSAA) (<http://dsaa2022.dsaa.co/>).
- International Conference on Artificial Intelligence in Medicine 2023 (<https://iaim2023.sg/>).
- International Conference on Artificial Intelligence in Medicine 2022 (<https://aime22.aimedicine.info/>).
- 2021 IEEE 34th International Symposium on Computer-Based Medical Systems (CBMS) (<https://cbms2021.web.ua.pt/>).

Next steps:

The ICCS team (IPR holder) is interested in further development of the CDSS in other research/development projects. The team seeks to increase accuracy, extend scope and test it in other sectors. Finally, the team already published and intend to publish further the results to relevant conferences and journals.

Discussions are ongoing on how the CDSS could potentially enter the market and what could be the role of the SMEs in the consortium. The UNITI Working Group will work towards the direction of identifying collaboration opportunities.

Further development and further validation is needed to reach a TRL of seven or eight. However, to the best of our knowledge no competition exists and despite the low TRL, there are positive market circumstances which with the appropriate actions, the CDSS could potentially become a commercial product.

2.2 UNITI mobile application

The UNITI Mobile App is a mobile framework available for iOS and Android. The overarching goal is the treatment of chronic tinnitus patients. Patients receive a module for psychoeducation, a module for sound stimulation and a module for the daily assessment of tinnitus (tinnitus diary).

Figure 2: UNITY mobile app (iOS and Android)

- iOS version: <https://apps.apple.com/uy/app/unity-tinnitus-study/>
- Android version: https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=com.dbis.haugxhaug.unity&hl=en_US

Exploitation achievements

Usage of the UNITY mobile app: Some very important statistics that showcase the extensive use of the UNITY mobile application are the following:

- **Tinnitus diary** > 40.000 questionnaires filled
- **Shades of noise** > 13.000 sessions
- **TinEdu**
 - Mini HQ-9 >350
 - Quizzes filled in > 5.000
 - Sections completed > 20.000

The partners (UHREG, UKW) that have been developing the UNITY mobile app will continue to maintain both versions. The mobile app will be open for everybody to use it.

Mobile app data (open): All data coming from the UNITY mobile app will be available for further research. The content of the structured counselling of the UNITY mobile app is already available at the project's Zenodo community here: <https://zenodo.org/record/8223780>. The plan is to open all data coming from the UNITY mobile app in the next six months. Data will be available at the project's Zenodo community and will be disseminated through the project's website.

Business model: The owners of the IPRs are already discussing about the future exploitation potential of the UNITI mobile app. There are several discussions with third parties about the funding of the UNITI mobile app in order to keep it alive. The UNITI mobile app business model is presented in Section 4.2.

Scientific publications: A number of scientific publications have been published based on data coming from the UNITI app. The most important are the following:

- Schlee, W., Kraft, R., Schobel, J., Langguth, B., Probst, T., Lourenco, M. P., ... & Pryss, R. (2023). Momentary assessment of tinnitus—How smart mobile applications advance our understanding of tinnitus. In *Digital Phenotyping and Mobile Sensing* (pp. 285-303). Springer, Cham. https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1007/978-3-030-31620-4_13
- Jamaludeen, N., Unnikrishnan, V., Pryss, R., Schobel, J., Schlee, W., & Spiliopoulou, M. (2021, June). Circadian Conditional Granger Causalities on Ecological Momentary Assessment Data from an mHealth App. In *2021 IEEE 34th International Symposium on Computer-Based Medical Systems (CBMS)* (pp. 354-359). IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/CBMS52027.2021.00110>.
- Vogel, C., Schobel, J., Schlee, W., Engelke, M., & Pryss, R. (2021). UNITI Mobile - EMI-Apps for a Large-Scale European Study on Tinnitus. ArXiv, abs/2107.14029. 43rd Annual International Conference of the IEEE Engineering in Medicine & Biology Society (EMBC).
- Engelke M, Simões J, Vogel C., Schoisswohl S, Schecklmann M, Wölflick S, Pryss R, Probst Th, Langguth B, Schlee W (2023). Pilot study of a smartphone-based tinnitus therapy using structured counseling and sound therapy: A multiple-baseline design with ecological momentary assessment. *PLOS Digit Health* 2(1): e0000183. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pdig.0000183>
- Schlee W, Neff P, Simoes J, Langguth B, Schoisswohl S, Steinberger H, Norman M, Spiliopoulou M, Schobel J, Hannemann R, Pryss R. Smartphone-Guided Educational Counseling and Self-Help for Chronic Tinnitus. *Journal of Clinical Medicine*. 2022; 11(7):1825. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jcm11071825>
- Allgaier, J., Schlee, W., Probst, T., & Pryss, R. (2022). Prediction of Tinnitus Perception Based on Daily Life MHealth Data Using Country Origin and Season. *Journal of Clinical Medicine*, 11(15), 4270. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jcm11154270>
- Shahania, S., Unnikrishnan, V., Pryss, R., Kraft, R., Schobel, J., Hannemann, R., ... & Spiliopoulou, M. (2022). Predicting Ecological Momentary Assessments in an App for

Tinnitus by Learning From Each User's Stream With a Contextual Multi-Armed Bandit. *Frontiers in neuroscience*, 16.

- Prakash S, Unnikrishnan V, Pryss R, Kraft R, Schobel J, Hannemann R, Langguth B, Schlee W, Spiliopoulou M. (2021) Interactive System for Similarity-Based Inspection and Assessment of the Well-Being of mHealth Users. *Entropy*. 2021; 23(12):1695. <https://doi.org/10.3390/e23121695>

Next steps:

- Continue support for the mobile apps. Both versions of the UNITI mobile app will continue to be functional for at least 2 years after the end of the project.
- Continue analysing data coming from the UNITI mobile app.
- Make all data open. The plan is to release all data coming from the mobile app as open at the project's Zenodo community.
- Identify new funding opportunities.
- A lot of discussions have already taken place by the main IPR holders (UHREG, UKW) towards identifying collaboration opportunities and commercializing the UNITI app.
- UNITI Working Group will work towards the direction of identifying collaboration opportunities, clarifying the IPRs and push towards the commercialization of the UNITI mobile app.

2.3 UNITI Randomised Clinical Trials

UNITI consortium conducted a multicenter, parallel-arm, randomised clinical trial involving patients with chronic subjective tinnitus. Patients were randomly assigned to a single or combinational treatment. A set of four different therapy approaches were used: cognitive-behavioral therapy, hearing aids, structured counseling, and sound therapy. All possible combinations of two treatments were tested. The primary outcome was the change from baseline to week 12 in the total score of the Tinnitus Handicap Inventory (THI). The most important research outputs from the RCTs will be presented on a manuscript that has been prepared. Some of the most important aspects of UNITI RCTs are the following:

- Results from one of the biggest RCTs in tinnitus / new methodological benchmark for tinnitus trials.
- First proper combination of therapeutic interventions for tinnitus (targeting different organ levels).
- If single or a combinational therapy is more effective as a treatment for tinnitus.

- Which type of single intervention or which specific combination of treatments produces superior results.
- Demographic, psychological, audiological, electrophysiological, and genetic patient data from different countries; all treated with interventions harmonized over all participating centers.
- The UNITI-RCT represents a very, if not even one of the most important factor of the entire UNITI-Project, since many important parts of other UNITI workpackages are integrated - e.g., gathering of blood samples for genetic analysis, recording of data for in-silico models, validation of the DSS, implementation of the developed UNITI mobile applications (m-health).
- Potential of reapplication of standardised UNITI-RCT methodology for future research projects.
- The used interventions in the UNITI-RCT have the potential for brief or even prolonged tinnitus suppression as well as to help people to better cope respectively live with their tinnitus.
- Increase of already established international reputation in research and clinical practice.

Exploitation activities: For the wider adoption of the methodological approaches and best practices of the UNITI RCTs a number of exploitation actions are foreseen:

- UNITI consortium has already prepared a manuscript and is working on a number of other scientific publications.
- Present the results of the RCTs to key stakeholders in the tinnitus domain. Preliminary results have already been presented to the Tinnitus Research Initiative conference 2023.
- RCT results were also presented to a number of doctors during the TRI (Tinnitus Research Initiative) Online Seminar Series (supported by UNITI project): <https://tinnitusresearch.net/index.php/tri-academy/tri-online-academy>.

Next steps:

- Continue support for the mobile apps. Both versions of the UNITI mobile app will continue to be functional for at least 3 years after the end of the project.
- Continue analysing data coming from the UNITI RCTs.
- Continue publishing the results on high impact factor journals and conferences.

- Make all data open. The plan is to release all data coming from the RCTs as open at the project's Zenodo community.
- Make the analysis code open. The plan is to release also the analysis script as open at the project's Zenodo community.
- New funding opportunities.

2.4 UNITI Genetics

UNITI is combining data from genetics and protein analysis with clinical research to improve diagnosis, prognosis and selection of personalized therapy in chronic tinnitus patients. The discovery of the genetic contribution to tinnitus is a major scientific challenge. The following are expected to be the most important outputs:

- Generation of a short list of candidate genes
- Proximity Extension Assay (PEA) will be used to search for protein biomarkers for tinnitus in a case-control study including Swedish patients with tinnitus.
- Generation of predictive genetic data towards personalisation of tinnitus treatment: Whole Genome Sequencing (WGS) will be conducted in patients participating in the RCT, who will provide relevant consent. Saliva samples will be used as source of DNA to perform WGS in the patients recruited in the RCT. Samples will be sequenced, after quality inspection. The goal is to obtain common (located in non-coding regions) and rare variants (exon) to analyse their potential interaction and the effect on the therapeutic intervention. To this end, WGS will be performed in order to generate SNV and structural variants. These variants will be used to generate an integral genomic dataset in tinnitus patients.
- Generation of predictive blood biomarker data towards personalisation of tinnitus treatment: ELISA or ELLA will be conducted on a selected set of biomarkers identified in 6.3. using plasma samples collected from patients participating in the RCT. These biomarkers will be investigated in order to determine whether they are associated with positive outcome in the RCTs.

Exploitation activities: For the wider exploitation of the results from the UNITI Genetics work, a number of exploitation actions are foreseen:

- Preparation of scientific publications that present the results.
- Preparation of demonstration materials and dissemination of these materials to appropriate target audience.

- Genetic results will be also presented to a number of doctors during the TRI (Tinnitus Research Initiative) Online Seminar Series that are being conducted with the support of UNITI project partners: <https://tinnitusresearch.net/index.php/tri-academy/tri-online-academy>.

2.5 Socio-economic impact of tinnitus

The current status of the scientific literature highlights a serious lack of studies estimating in detail the economic burden of tinnitus to healthcare systems, patients, their families and society. Identifying the economic burden of tinnitus in various cost categories is crucial to better understand tinnitus healthcare organization and treatment implementability in current practice in various countries and consequently reduce unnecessary costly and ineffective treatment strategies for patients and healthcare systems.

Exploitation activities: For the wider exploitation of the results from the UNITI socio-economic impact work, a number of exploitation actions have been implemented:

- Preparation of a manuscript with the results of the UNITI socio-economic impact study.
- Preparation of demonstration materials / policy recommendations with the outcomes of the study and dissemination of these materials to appropriate target audience / policy makers.
- Presentation of the results to TRI 2023 conference in Dublin (June 2023).
- Develop an updated version of the UNITI socio-economic impact questionnaire. A questionnaire with more than 45 questions was developed by the UNITI team to be able to calculate the socio-economic costs of tinnitus. Based on the analysis of the results, a number of recommendations will be proposed, and a new version of the survey (Appendix I: UNITI Socioeconomic survey (updated version)) will be made available for the tinnitus community to use. The questionnaire will be widely disseminated through the UNITI website and the TRI channels.

Next steps:

- Make all survey data open. The socio-economic impact team is planning to release all data coming from the UNITI socio-economic survey as open at the project's Zenodo community.
- Results will be also presented to a number of doctors during the TRI (Tinnitus Research Initiative) Online Seminar Series that are being conducted with the support of UNITI project partners: <https://tinnitusresearch.net/index.php/tri-academy/tri-online-academy>

2.6 UNITI data

During the project, many types of data have been collected. The most important are the following:

- questionnaire data from the RCTs,
- UNITI mobile app data,
- blood data,
- laboratory tests,
- hearing aid data,
- data from the socio-economic survey,
- UNITI big online study.

Figure 3: UNITI data

All UNITI partners are already working on analysing this data. What is really interesting also is to look at the connections between the different datasets. UNITI consortium has already formed groups that are working on that direction.

Exploitation actions:

- **Scientific publications:** A significant number of UNITI scientific publications focused on analysing and presenting all this data that have been collected within the UNITI project. Without UNITI data it would be impossible to create this huge amount of work with regards to the scientific publications.

Next steps:

- **Open access:** The most important exploitation output with regards to UNITI data is that there is a plan to open UNITI data to the public. All UNITI data will be available to UNITI's Zenodo community.
- **Further analysis of the results:** All UNITI partners will continue to work on analysing the data and on looking at the connections between the different datasets.

2.7 Further important technical outcomes

In this section we present some very important technical outputs of UNITI project that have already been published to a number of scientific journals and have been presented to relevant conferences (see Section **Error! Reference source not found.**). These outputs have low TRL. The research teams behind these outputs will continue to further develop them and identify opportunities to test their replicability to other domains.

All these outputs are also presented to the Horizon Results Platform (<https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/horizon-results-platform>) with the aim to seek for synergies, further funding opportunities and collaborations with the European research community.

A brief description of the outputs is presented:

2.7.1 A Contextual Multi-armed Bandit Method to Develop Patient-Centric Prediction Models

Shall we predict a patient's condition from the patient's past data only? Is it better to consider also data from other patients for the prediction, or is there a risk of contaminating the model because patients may be very dissimilar? We propose a method that monitors patients who interact with an mHealth app and finds a good balance between predictors that see only a single patient's data, those that see the patient's neighbourhood, and the global model trained on all patients. The method's core is a contextual multi-armed bandit that assesses the expected reward.

It was found that the contextual multi-armed bandit can leverage the patient context to choose between data-intensive and data-sparing methods to maximise overall prediction quality over all users. The users who interacted with the system for the longest time gained the most in terms of prediction quality from the personalised models. The contextual multi-armed bandit was trained to minimise regret as measured by RMSE of multi-output hoeffding adaptive

regressors trained on single patient EMAs, patient-neighbourhood EMAs, and a global model trained over all EMA data available.

Figure 4: A Contextual Multi-armed Bandit Method to Develop Patient-Centric Prediction Models

2.7.2 Interactive System for Similarity-Based Inspection and Assessment of the Well-Being of mHealth Users

As mHealth apps proliferate and can be used for the monitoring of chronic diseases, clinicians need tools for this monitoring. The method showcases a GUI web application that assists the clinician in inspecting the symptom progression of, and in visualising the short-term predictions for a patient's disease progression.

The web application allows the clinician to inspect the patient's data, as well as identify outliers and look at the predicted progression of the disease. The visualisation methods developed incorporate the dynamic data of the symptoms as well as static patient characteristics age, gender, etc. The predictions are delivered by a linear regressor trained over the user's neighbourhood as defined over their static properties.

Figure 5: Interactive System for Similarity-Based Inspection and Assessment of the Well-Being of mHealth Users

2.7.3 COBALT – a cost-aware method for the discovery of predictive subgroups

How to choose the best treatment for a patient among different candidate treatments? Ideally, one would predict the treatment outcome for each candidate. With COBALT, we predict the outcome of each candidate treatment while minimizing the amount of information that needs to be recorded before treatment. Why minimize the information demand? Because some medical examinations demand expensive equipment, and all examinations demand time. Even self-assessment questionnaires demand time and they often incur patient burden. COBALT is cost-aware and selects the questionnaires (scores) and variables in a parsimonious way.

COBALT spans a multi-layer network over the patient assessments using the Leiden method to find subgroups, allowing for assessments that have not been completed by all patients. It derives patient subgroups by incrementally adding assessments (questionnaire scores, medical examinations) so that subgroup quality and predictive quality remain high and the diversity of subgroups increases with the addition of layers. The incremental addition of assessments contributes to cost awareness. The subgroup quality and diversity allow for the construction of phenotypes. To facilitate phenotyping, we also provide compact visualizations.

We tested COBALT with tinnitus questionnaire data from one of the UNITI RCT clinics. We have shown that the COBALT-induced subgroups improved the prediction of the treatment outcome when compared with (i) no subgroup information and (ii) subgroups discovered with traditional clustering algorithms.

Figure 6: COBALT – a cost-aware method for the discovery of predictive subgroups

2.7.4 Neighbourhood based methods for predictions on sparse mHealth data

When prescribed to use an mHealth app, some users interact intensively with it, while others interact casually and/or pause for longer periods of time. The less data a user delivers, the more difficult it is to predict how his/her condition will develop. To what extent can we leverage such a prediction with data from users who deliver more information?

We propose a method that finds for each user those users whose data can improve prediction. The method collects data iteratively, and identifies users who enhance the predictors of many other users. This forms the basis of a selective augmentation of a user’s model with data from other users, avoiding the risk of contaminating the augmented model with irrelevant information.

Our method allows that users respond on irregular intervals and that not all questions are answered.

Given the data from the mHealth application, our algorithm builds up an informative personalized neighbourhood for each user, exploiting both baseline data and data during the interaction with the mHealth app. In our experiments with the UNITI app as part of the UNITI RCT, we have shown that this personalized neighbourhood leads to a small but significant increase in quality for the task of predicting the development of the patient’s condition during the patient monitoring period.

A further result concerns the contribution of each user to the augmentation of models of other users. We found that a small subset of users were almost universally absent from the

personalized neighbourhoods built for the individual users. The scientific cause of this is not yet well understood, but this form of outlieriness serves as a useful focus for future investigations.

The image below shows that there is a small band of users that are almost universally absent in other users' neighbourhoods (black vertical band in centre-right), while others are in the neighbourhood of almost all users.

Figure 7: Neighbourhood based methods for predictions on sparse mHealth data

2.8 Assessment of UNITI outputs/innovations

In principle, through the different UNITI outputs the project is proving to be impactful and beneficial to the field of tinnitus research in several ways. Overall, UNITI has created a **huge impact** with regards to **advancing the level of knowledge and skills in the tinnitus field**, as well as **raising awareness of ongoing issues in the management of tinnitus and the socio-economic challenges it poses**. These insights will be impactful far beyond the duration of the UNITI project and clearly transcend the tinnitus field, impacting on other domains as well.

There are outputs that have very impactful research results such as the RCTs, the Genetics, and the socio-economic impact of tinnitus. These results have been appropriately disseminated to key stakeholders (tinnitus clinical centres, doctors, tinnitus patients, tinnitus associations, policy makers etc.) and the consortium is willing to continue disseminating this work further even after the end of the project.

At the same time, there are tools and methods with very high research impact on the tinnitus domain and the results can be transferred to other domains as well. These results have already been appropriately disseminated to key stakeholders and at the same time they are about to be exploited so that key stakeholders can also make use of these tools.

Finally, there are technical outputs (**UNITI mobile app**) with high TRL that have already been used by a big number of users. A large number of individuals have registered in the app and use it on a daily basis. UNITI consortium has already disclosed innovative knowledge on the predictive tinnitus model generated from high numbers of patient data in the databases and used it to create a novel integrated **UNITI CDSS**. For these outputs that have commercialization potential, we conducted a SWOT analysis in “D8.2 Exploitation plan and innovation management report”, we provided recommendations on the actions that need to be further implemented to enhance their commercialization potential and we present in Section 4 their business models. Before discussing about the commercialization opportunities, we provide an overview of the IPRs involved (Section 3).

3 Intellectual Property Rights

According to “World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO)”¹, Intellectual Property Rights (IPRs) are the legal rights which result from intellectual activity in the industrial, scientific, literary and artistic fields. IPRs cover two main areas:

- industrial property (inventions: patents, utility models; trademarks; industrial designs and protected designations of origin), and
- copyright (represented by literary, musical, artistic, photographic and audio-visual works).

In UNITI, as in every other EU research project, there are two IPR issues that need to be handled. First of all, **the management of the pre-existing know-how (background IPRs)** that exist in terms of commercialisation of the final product/service/result, and secondly **how the knowledge generated within the project (foreground IPRs) should be protected** by the UNITI consortium after the end of the project. This section provides a first analysis of these issues (keeping in mind that the project is still in progress and the project outputs have not been yet completed).

¹ <http://www.wipo.int/>

Background IPRs are Intellectual Property Rights that existed before the beginning of project. It is knowledge held by participants prior to their accession to the Grand Agreement, as well as any IPRs which are needed for carrying out the project. In UNITI, there are Background IPRs reported by the consortium and stated in the UNITI Consortium Agreement. The Background IPRs that are relevant to the exploitation plan are the following:

Describe Background	Specific limitations and/or conditions for implementation (Article 25.2 Grant Agreement)	Specific limitations and/or conditions for Exploitation (Article 25.3 Grant Agreement)
Existing smartphone apps for tinnitus tracking, tinnitus matching, structured counselling and sound stimulation are under joint ownership of UHREG (Schlee) and UKW (Pryss).	They will be freely available to all UNITI parties during the lifetime of this project.	Can be discussed on a case by case scenario and subject to fair and reasonable licence conditions.
UHREG is the owner of the Database, which will be used for the collection of RCT Data within UNITI.	The functionalities of the EU Tinnitus Database will be available for the UNITI members at no costs.	Can be discussed on a case by case scenario and subject to fair and reasonable licence conditions.

Foreground IPRs are usually results, materials and knowledge generated in the project. They are IPRs that are generated within the project period and owned by the participant who generated them. When foreground is generated jointly, it is jointly owned, unless participants concerned agree on a different solution. In UNITI foreground IPRs are divided in two categories:

- The ones that were generated within the project period and belong to the UNITI Consortium such as the project logo and the project acronym.
- The ones that were generated within the project period and belong to participant(s) who generated them.

For the first category (IPRs belonging to the UNITI Consortium) we identify the following:

- The **project logo**, and the **project acronym** (UNITI) belong to the UNITI consortium. After the end of the project, the logo and the acronym will belong to the members of the consortium that are interested in the sustainability, exploitation and commercialisation of the project's results.

For the second category (Foreground IPRs belonging to one or more partners), we identify the outputs that have exploitation potential. An analysis of the IPRs of these outputs is presented in the Table below.

Table 1: Analysis of the IPRs involved in UNITI outcomes

UNITI output	Partners Involved	Licensing Options
UNITI CDSS core1	ICCS	Non-free.
UNITI mobile App	UKW, UHREG (the involvement of the clinical centres remains to be defined)	Content of the Psychoeducation module is open: CC BY 4.0
UNITI CDSS core2	MAG	Non-free.
Discovering mHealth User Neighbourhoods	MAG	Open source
Interactive Exploration of mHealth User Data With Multimodal Similarities	MAG	Open source
Results from the UNITI Randomized Clinical Trials	UHREG, UOA, CHA, GRA, KI	The research results will be publicly available through scientific publications, best practices, new methods. The contributors will be mentioned.

Genetics	GRA, KI	The research results will be publicly available through scientific publications, best practices, new methods. The contributors will be mentioned.
Socio-economic impact of tinnitus	VIL, MIL, UHREG, UOA	The research results will be publicly available through scientific publications. The contributors will be mentioned.

4 UNITI business models

In “D8.2 Exploitation plan and innovation management report” we evaluated the UNITI project outputs in terms of their innovation and commercialization potential. We concluded that UNITI CDSS and UNITI mobile app are two outputs that in the appropriate circumstances could be commercialized. We conducted a SWOT analysis to understand where we are and what actions need to be further implemented so that both outputs can enter the market as products.

We concluded with a list of actions that need to be implemented for realizing UNITI outputs' commercialization potential. These actions are described in D8.2 and are summarized in Section 4. In this section, we present the business models of the UNITI CDSS and the UNITI mobile app. The identification of UNITI value propositions has been constantly discussed and debated among the project partners since the beginning of the project and will continue to be one of the main points of discussion for the UNITI Working Group that has been established (Section 8).

The main objective of this business model exercise is to help consortium partners move beyond research-centric thinking and towards business model thinking.

This is a first attempt by the UNITI consortium to present the UNITI business models. We need to consider that business modeling is the managerial equivalent of the scientific method—we start with a hypothesis, which we then test in action and revise when necessary. Thus, these business models will be constantly evaluated and revised both by the UNITI working group and by external stakeholders (industry, funds etc.).

4.1 UNITI CDSS business model

Customers served: The main customers in this business model are the **Healthcare professionals** (including, but not limited to, audiologists, otolaryngologists, psychologists, physiotherapists, psychiatrists, licensed clinical social workers, dentists, and physical therapists) involved in tinnitus patient care. They require support in their attempt to identify the best treatment paths for people suffering from tinnitus.

What is UNITI CDSS offering to its customers (value proposition): There is an urgent need in the EU and worldwide for individualized predictions of the outcomes of tinnitus treatment approaches. UNITI CDSS can facilitate well-informed decision making. It is a user-friendly platform, able to suggest specific examinations according to individual patient’s profile and optimal treatment strategy based on the sum of collected data. The introduction of this mechanism aims to **reduce the workload** of the healthcare professionals during daily practice.

Furthermore, the use of UNITI CDSS can significantly reduce tinnitus-related costs for European healthcare systems. Reduction of these costs and increased efficiency of targeted treatment are beneficial for European economies and taxpayers.

How are customers being reached (channels):

The “Channels” element in the Business Model Canvas refers to the various methods or channels through which a business communicates with and delivers value to its customer segments. This is the medium through which the CDSS can provide its value proposition to its customers:

- For creating **awareness** there are marketing and advertising channels that should be considered: Personal face to face meetings with healthcare professionals / Participation to events where healthcare professionals meet / Internet and social media / Emails to healthcare professionals / third party health retailers / marketing campaigns.
- For **evaluation**: videos and a trial should allow healthcare professionals evaluate the CDSS before deciding to buy it.
- For **purchase and delivery**: healthcare professionals will have access to the CDSS online via the product website.
- For **support** there will be an after sales support service both through the website (email) and via telephone.

What relationships are we establishing with customers:

The CDSS will provide all the required functionalities for healthcare professionals to easily use it online. The customer’s online and buying behaviour will be monitored and used to provide suggestions on what should be improved. Customers will be supported with the latest updated versions of the CDSS and will have personal support.

Trial period: CDSS may have a trial period (1-2 months).

Limited functionality versions: CDSS may also be offered limited functionalities on its free version, with increased functions available to paying users.

What are customers willing to pay for and how (revenue streams):

- A fee for having access to the CDSS online version.
- A fee for support (platform updates as after sales care): a fee per year may be charged to customers that are using the CDSS support services. Such functionalities may include access to aggregate information and direct support services, etc.

What are the resources that underpin this business model: In order to be able to support this business model, UNITI CDSS needs human time from:

- Software engineers (to continuously update the CDSS platform).
- Business development personnel (to form and secure partnerships with relevant stakeholders from the healthcare sector).
- Customer support (responsible for providing support to existing customers).

Further resources needed are the following:

- Cloud infrastructure for hosting the UNITI CDSS.
- Offices.
- Subscription to healthcare related forums.

Which activities are needed in this business model: The organisation to implement this business model will need to maintain the UNITI CDSS which includes support and continuous update of the product (new data, new updated algorithms etc.). Furthermore, marketing and sales activities will be needed to gain new customers and to maintain the existing ones. In summary, the following are needed:

- **Research and development** that includes maintenance, product updates and new product development.
- **Business development** activities are needed to secure partnerships with healthcare institutions, associations and services, and also to mobilise a community of healthcare professionals.
- **Customer support** should ensure the proper operation of the UNITI CDSS platform 24/7.

Which partners leverage this business model: Tinnitus Associations (e.g. British Tinnitus Association, American Tinnitus Association), Hearing Loss Associations and the Tinnitus Research Initiative are key partners that may offer dissemination opportunities for the UNITI CDSS. Further partnerships with key stakeholders in the area of Tinnitus treatments should also be the main goal of the organization that will run the UNITI CDSS platform.

Which key resources / activities are most expensive (costs): The main costs for this business model are:

- Human resources (software engineers) are needed for maintaining the UNITI CDSS and developing new product features.
- Marketing and advertising to secure partnerships and sales.
- Participation to relevant events and conferences.

4.2 UNITI mobile app business model

Customers served: The main customers in this business model are **patients suffering from tinnitus**. Tinnitus affects more than 10% of the general population, whereas 1% of the population considers tinnitus as their major issue affecting their health.

What is UNITI mobile app offering to its customers (value proposition): The overarching goal of the UNITI mobile app is the **treatment of chronic tinnitus patients**. Patients receive a module for psychoeducation, a module for sound stimulation and a module for the daily assessment of tinnitus (tinnitus diary).

How are customers being reached (channels):

The channels through which the UNITI mobile app can provide its value proposition to its customers are the following:

- For creating **awareness** there are marketing and advertising channels that should be considered: Meetings with patient organisations / Internet and social media / Contact healthcare professionals / third party health retailers / marketing campaigns.

- For **evaluation**: videos and a trial should allow tinnitus patients evaluate the UNITI mobile before deciding to buy it.
- For **purchase and delivery**: tinnitus patients will have access to the mobile app online via the applications stores of Android and iOS.
- For **support** there will be an after-sales support service through the website (email). The website will also include FAQ.

What relationships are we establishing with customers:

The mobile app will provide all the required functionalities for tinnitus patients to easily use it through their mobile phones. The customer's online and buying behaviour will be monitored and used to provide suggestions on what should be improved. Customers will be supported with the latest updated versions of the mobile app and will receive email support.

Trial period: The mobile app may have a trial period (e.g. 1 month).

Limited functionality versions: The mobile app may also be offered with limited functionalities on its free version.

What are customers willing to pay for and how (revenue streams):

- A (monthly or yearly) fee for having access to the UNITI mobile app.

What are the resources that underpin this business model: To be able to support this business model, the entity that will run the UNITI mobile app needs human time from:

- Software developers (to continuously update the UNITI mobile app).
- Business development personnel (to form and secure partnerships with relevant stakeholders from the healthcare sector).
- Customer support (to provide support to existing customers).

Which activities are needed in this business model: The organisation to implement this business model will need to maintain the UNITI mobile app which includes support and continuous update of the product based on the latest research results. Furthermore, marketing and sales activities will be needed to gain new customers and to maintain the existing ones. In summary, the following are needed:

- **Research and development** that includes maintenance, product updates and new product development.

- **Business development** activities are needed to secure partnerships with healthcare institutions, patient associations and services, and to mobilise a community of tinnitus patients.
- **Customer support** should ensure the proper operation of the UNITI mobile app 24/7.

Which partners leverage this business model: Tinnitus Associations (e.g. British Tinnitus Association, American Tinnitus Association), Tinnitus Patient organisations, Hearing Loss Associations and the Tinnitus Research Initiative are key partners that may offer dissemination opportunities for the UNITI mobile app. Further partnerships with key stakeholders in the area of Tinnitus treatments should also be the main goal of the organization that will run the UNITI mobile app.

Which key resources / activities are most expensive (costs): The main costs for this business model are:

- Human resources (software developers) are needed for maintaining the UNITI mobile app and developing new product features.
- Marketing and advertising to secure partnerships and sales.
- Participation to relevant events and conferences.

5 Commercialization and business plan

The UNITI partners strongly believe that awareness, and targeted dissemination activities are crucial to exploit the UNITI results and mobilise a community around them. UNITI partners intend to support such activities as much as possible even after the end of the project and continue maintaining and supporting the UNITI research outputs for an initial period of at least two years (mainly through the UNITI Working Group). Further development may be performed by academic and commercial partners, provided the appropriate (internal to the partners or external) resources can be found and allocated. Hackathons (already organized two during the project lifetime) will be planned by academic partners and support for these will be sought from the industry. Seminars and training will be offered in academic institutions, and participation to conferences will be sought to further present the project results. Further validation and standardization activities may be sought by the partners developing the CDSS and the mobile app. Partnerships with industry will be sought.

To suggest follow-up actions, we started on the premise that exploitation depends not only on what is available at the end of the project, but also on what will be maintained after the project's

termination. In this latter front, the **UNITI mobile app** will be maintained by UHREG and UKW and the **UNITI CDSS** will be maintained by ICCS.

The steps that we took in the UNITI project have been quite significant to start opening the market for services tailored to tinnitus patients and tinnitus-related healthcare professionals. What we did in UNITI is that we pioneered and assessed the feasibility of developing services for the tinnitus community. We have provided the necessary infrastructure for testing this notion, and we are committed to maintain this infrastructure for further research. We proved our concept to be correct and our approach very useful for tinnitus patients.

Below we describe a short-term action plan that the UNITI consortium is committed to implement after the end of the project:

- The **UNITI mobile app will be maintained** by UHREG and UKW (for at least two years after the end of the project). Towards this direction, a startup has been established by the core members of both teams with the aim to identify further commercialization opportunities.
- The **UNITI CDSS will be maintained** by ICCS (for at least two years after the end of the project). ICCS has already established an open dialogue with UNITI SMEs (VIL, SPX) and other industrial partners that expressed their interest in the research results of the UNITI CDSS. The possibility to establish a spin-off is also being considered after a more detailed evaluation of the UNITI CDSS business model by investors.
- The **UNITI working group** (Section 8) will be established with the core aim to further exploit the project's results. Exploitation, sustainability and business potential of all the UNITI outputs especially the UNITI mobile app and CDSS will be the core items in the agenda of the working group.
- The **UNITI business models** (Section 4) will be further validated by policy makers, industrial partners and funds. The business models (together with a pitching presentation) will be presented to relevant start-up events.
- UNITI mobile app and UNITI CDSS will continue to be presented to relevant **conferences** and **events** around the world.
- The strong relationships between UNITI consortium and the **Tinnitus Research Initiative** and **Tinnitus Associations** around the world will keep going with the aim to widely disseminate all the knowledge generated during the project.
- The **project website** will be maintained for at least five years after the end of the project and will include detailed information about the project results.

- **SMEs** in the consortium are committed to provide support services both to ICCS and to UHREG and UKW for commercializing the UNITI CDSS and mobile app respectively.
- Further **funding opportunities** will be sought. Consortium partners have already applied for further funding.

6 Summary of exploitation actions implemented

To effectively promote the UNITI outputs and address how they will reach the target audiences, UNITI has established a dissemination and exploitation strategy. UNITI has selected the kind of tools and channels that are going to be utilised to realise the project's dissemination and exploitation actions. Various online and offline means, direct and indirect, were necessary to make the project activities and results available to the target groups. Such methods are manifold, including online options (website, emails, social media), mass media and networks (media presence, social networks, partners' networks etc.), or offline tangible actions, like events, posters, brochures etc. Depending on the project's audiences the adequate set of methods are jointly being employed.

6.1 UNITI Publications

Publications are the most significant element for UNITI exploitation strategy; they constitute an important exploitation tool that informs and engages the UNITI community about and with the projects' procedures, methodologies and outcomes. So far a big number **scientific publications** have been published and are available on the project website here: <https://uniti.tinnitusresearch.net/index.php/research/scientific-publications>. It is worth mentioning that more publications are coming since the consortium has already submitted new manuscripts to scientific journals.

UNITI scientific publications are actually the legacy of the project to the tinnitus community. The huge effort that all partners made, to publish the results to high impact factor journals and to present them to established conferences showcase how UNITI advanced the state-of-the-art in the tinnitus field.

6.2 UNITI project website

The project's website (<https://uniti.tinnitusresearch.net>) operates as the major source about the project's identity, goals and actions, from which every stakeholder category can be informed. In other words, UNITI website is a central dissemination and exploitation tool of the project providing the main results of the UNITI research and outcomes. In particular, the UNITI website aims at:

- Providing information about the project, its main objective, description of the produced outputs and knowledge, publications, latest news and upcoming events in which UNITI will participate, information about project partners and related projects introduction with a link to their websites, subscription to project’s newsletter, social networks and contact info.
- Presenting information to stakeholders so that they will understand the reasons to get involved and how they can participate in the project’s activities.

So far, more than 80 news items have been published on the UNITI website, informing the audience about the status of the project and the progress of the main exploitable outputs.

The website will continue to operate even after the end of the project informing the tinnitus community about.

6.3 Exploitation results and achievements

Overall, all UNITI partners implemented a significant number of exploitation actions to ensure that both the knowledge generated during the project will remain (publicly accessible) and that appropriate actions are made to explore the sustainability (and commercialization) potential of some important components even after the project ends.

In the table below we present all the technical outputs, grouped by lead developer, the current Technology Readiness Level (TRL) of the components and the main actions implemented in terms of Dissemination and Exploitation.

UNITI output	Owner	TRL	Blog post	Horizon Results Platform	Research work implemented
CDSS core1	ICSS	4			> 4 publications 1 PhD
CDSS core2	MAG	4			> 10 publications 1 PhD
UNITI mobile App	UKW, UHREG	7			> 8 publications
A Contextual Multi-armed Bandit Method to	MAG	3			> 5 publications

Develop Patient-Centric Prediction Models					
Interactive System for Similarity-Based Inspection and Assessment of the Well-Being of mHealth Users	MAG	3			> 6 publications
COBALT – a cost-aware method for the discovery of predictive subgroups	MAG	3			> 4 publications
Neighbourhood based methods for predictions on sparse mHealth data	MAG	3			> 5 publications

7 Partners' exploitation activities and impact

In UNITI we undertook all measures and tools to pursue the goal of “opening the eyes” and “guiding” project partners through to a structured process of successful exploitation. All partners were familiar with the terms such as what is an exploitation plan, what is sustainability etc., and all partners did their best to make the knowledge generated during the project available to a wide target audience. Below we present an analysis of the impact and exploitation paths for UNITI partners.

Clinical centres (UHREG, UOA, CHA, GRA, KUL, KI):

- Possibility of reusing implemented UNITI treatment protocols and the EU tinnitus database in all clinical partner sites.

- Reapplication of standardised UNITI RCT methodology for future research projects, thereby enhancing the comparability across the European Research Area and potentially worldwide in the long term.
- Continue using the UNITI mobile app to implement Ecological Momentary Assessment from tinnitus patients.
- Further increase of already established international reputation in research and clinical practice by being participant of UNITI and the largest RCT in tinnitus.
- International visibility and recognition as specialized tinnitus clinic.
- Immediate benefits for all staff members by participating in international consortium due to cooperation and networks formed, enabling fruitful scientific exchange.
- PhD students, post-docs and senior post-docs are benefiting from outstanding publication record and will be able to use UNITI's scientific outcomes for research and industry career advancement, e.g. by gaining academic degrees or through established industry contacts.

Technical partners (MAG, UKW, ICCS):

- Enhancement of existing technological expertise in terms of delivering secure and interoperable solutions on e-health related tools and services.
- Utilisation of UNITI's technical solutions in future research projects.
- Technical knowledge transfer of UNITI's scientific frameworks to other medical related projects and conditions as well.
- Application of a variety of modern data analysis tools on the largest clinical data set in tinnitus.
- Profiting from extension of network with clinical partners and possibility of extensive publishing in domains of medicine and data science increasing international reputation.
- Gaining further expertise and momentum in the relevant areas of personalised treatment, mHealth and decision support systems.
- Expansion of international networks and cooperation in tinnitus research.
- Increasing the international visibility as an institution advancing technical solutions in medicine.
- PhD students, post-docs and senior post-docs will benefit from outstanding publication record and will be able to use UNITI's scientific outputs for research and industry career advancement, e.g. by gaining academic degrees or through established industry contacts

Genetic research (GRA, KI):

- Collection of unique data on genetic and blood biomarker in tinnitus.
- Reapplication of standardised UNITI research methodology in current and future research projects.
- Re-utilisation of gathered genetic data for further analyses with potential future techniques.
- Establishment of the institutions as leading organisations in the tinnitus genetics field worldwide.
- Expansion of international networks and cooperation in tinnitus research.
- International visibility and recognition as leading scientific institution for genetics on tinnitus.
- PhD students, post-docs and senior post-docs will benefit from outstanding publication record and will be able to use UNITI's scientific outputs for research and industry career advancement, e.g. by gaining academic degrees or through established industry contacts.

Epidemiological research (MIL):

- Reapplication of standardised UNITI research methodology for future research projects, thereby enhancing the comparability across the European Research Area and potentially worldwide in the long term.
- Further increase and strengthening of national and international reputation in tinnitus epidemiology.

SMEs (VIL, SPX)

- UNITI to enrich and further develop practical and digital innovative solutions for the growing and demanding healthcare sector.
- Gaining valuable experience in highly relevant area of tinnitus research and treatment.
- Increase of international visibility and reputation of SME through participation in UNITI consortium, likely adding to attraction for future commercial investors or academic partners on national and international level.
- Position in international research world and secure future clients and cooperating partners in Europe and worldwide.
- Become professional advisor to start-ups potentially deriving from UNITI.

8 UNITI working group

In order to make sure that the UNITI knowledge will be sustained and widely exploited to European stakeholders and that appropriate actions will be made in order to explore the sustainability, business and replication potential of the UNITI tools, we propose the development of a Working Group that will take up the results, will continue working in the UNITI area and will focus on sustaining the UNITI tools.

The **UNITI Working Group** (in brief UNITI WG) is a group of individuals (under the umbrella of the UNITI project) that are interested - from a scientific and practical point of view - on the topics that were addressed by the UNITI project throughout its whole duration.

It will be formed in an informal way, as a network of individuals, after the UNITI project's closure and will consist initially of persons that have been actively involved in all the phases of UNITI contributing to the project's know-how.

The main aim of the Working Group is to capture the momentum that has been generated and exploit the project results on a voluntary basis while at the same time promote tinnitus research. UNITI WG intends to:

- a. Disseminate the project's results and findings to key stakeholders.
- b. Capitalise the outputs of the project and seek ways of exploiting, sustaining and commercializing its legacies.
- c. Provide visibility to the persons involved in the project, as well as some kind of credibility in terms of their expertise on the topics addressed by the project.
- d. Sustain the regular contact and communication among its members towards future and further Research and Innovation activities relevant to tinnitus.
- e. Strongly collaborate with the Tinnitus Associations around the world in order exploit the project results to a wide target audience.
- f. Identify further funding opportunities for tinnitus research.

The specific objectives of the Working Group for the upcoming twelve months are:

- To discuss the composition of a UNITI WG manifesto (declaration).
- To discuss the management structure of the WG.
- To organise (online or offline) Working Group meetings every three months that should run according to an announced agenda that is distributed well in advance of the meeting itself.

- To exploit the project results as these are presented in this document and in the respective UNITI deliverables.
- To discuss on the commercialization potential of UNITI CDSS, and UNITI mobile app.
- To continue discussions around the broad topic of tinnitus treatment. The working group will have a mailing list and a wiki where discussions around the UNITI topics will take place.
- To keep the project's website active by posting relevant news items and informing about the Working Group's activities. The target is to post at least 1 article per month. The names of the authors will be displayed in each post.
- To identify new research opportunities and collaboratively work on the preparation of research proposals in relation to the UNITI.
- To discuss about adding new members to the working group. Experts can express their interest and the working group can discuss every six months and decide whether they should be included or not.
- To seek for sponsors that will provide financial support to the Working Group.

The UNITI WG could include in next phases of its existence, other individuals that were not involved in the UNITI project. This way, it could be established either formally or informally as a broader open network.

The main dissemination tools of the UNITI WG will be the project's website. The specific timeline for next major activities of the WG include the following:

1. The Working Group is being setup (kick-off). The members will be included in the project's website. (M1 – December 2023).
2. The Working Group manifesto is ready (M3 – February 2024).
3. The section on the website for the Working Group is ready. The website will be restructured to accommodate the Working Group needs but the content that is already there will still exist (M4 – March 2024).
4. Wide online and offline dissemination campaign will take place informing about the establishment of the Working Group. A press release will be created and will be sent to relevant contacts. Our aim is to inform stakeholders about our activities. (M5 – April 2024).
5. Wide online and offline dissemination campaign of the UNITI tools will take place (M5 – April 2024).

- The Working Group has a management structure that has been agreed by all members. Roles are being allocated to members (M6 – May 2024)

Figure 8: Timeline for important WG activities

9 Conclusions

UNITI project delivered important results for the tinnitus research community. This document describes the most important UNITI results and the most important dissemination and exploitation actions that have been carried out by UNITI consortium. The consortium worked towards the following directions: scientific publications, openness and identification of commercialization opportunities. The large number of scientific publications focused on making UNITI results available to a wide number of researchers and healthcare professionals interested in the field of tinnitus. At the same time, by making UNITI data open and accessible to all researchers, UNITI consortium supports the exploitation and sustainability of UNITI results allowing other researchers to work on further analysing UNITI datasets and tools. The business and commercialization potential of the UNITI CDSS and UNITI mobile app have been evaluated (D8.2) and business models have been prepared.

With this document we have set the environment for the dissemination, exploitation and commercialization of the UNITI results. The UNITI working group that is now formed, will capitalise on UNITI research and will work towards further exploiting UNITI results and on identifying further funding opportunities to continue the work for tinnitus treatments.

Appendix I: UNITI Socioeconomic survey (updated version)

Tinnitus out-of-pocket costs questionnaire

Introduction:

Dear participant, with this survey we hope to gain insights into the financial burden for the individual, as well as for the society, associated with suffering from tinnitus.

In this survey, we will use the term “tinnitus” to identify the perception of a sound in one or both ears, or in the head, when no external sound is present in the environment. Oftentimes a ringing or buzzing sound is reported.

We would like to kindly ask you to reply to the questions below as accurately as possible. Your answers will be stored safely and anonymously following the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) rules.

Some sections of the questionnaire will ask you general questions while others are to be answered in regard to the past twelve months. Please read the introductions for the different sections carefully so you know how to approach the questions.

Most questions are compulsory, meaning an answer will be required before moving on, but where appropriate you will be able to answer "Do not know" or "Other".

The approximate time to complete this questionnaire is estimated to 10 minutes approximately.

Acknowledgements: The realization of the present questionnaire has been supported by UNITI project. UNITI has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme, Grant Agreement Number 848261

I Agree to participate in the study and I Agree with the data privacy policy

We will ask you a few questions on hearing issues and on the sensation of noise in head or in one or both ears, which is a symptom that medical doctors call “tinnitus”.

Part A – Tinnitus characteristics

1. Over the past year, have you had noises (such as ringing or buzzing) in your head or in one or both ears that last for more than five minutes at a time?

- Yes, most or all of the time
- Yes, a lot of the time
- Yes, some of the time
- No, not in the past year. Thank you for your time it is not required to complete the questionnaire
- No, never. Thank you for your time it is not required to complete the questionnaire
- Do not know/Prefer not to answer. Thank you for your time it is not required to complete the questionnaire

2. Over the past year, how much did these noises in your head or ears worry, annoy or upset you when they were at their worst?

- Severely
- Moderately
- Slightly
- Not at all
- Do not know/Prefer not to answer

3. Over the past year, have you seen your family doctor or another healthcare professional for problems with noises in your head or ears?

- Yes, 5 or more visits
- Yes, 2 to 4 visits
- Yes, one visit
- No
- Do not know/Prefer not to answer

4. Do you currently have any other difficulty with your hearing, such as listening to speech in a noisy situation?

- Yes, cannot hear at all
- Yes, severe difficulty
- Yes, moderate difficulty
- Yes, slight difficulty
- No difficulty
- Do not know/Prefer not to answer

5. How many years ago did your tinnitus appear?

- Less than a year ago
- 1-5 year ago
- 6-9 years ago
- 10-19 years ago
- 20 or more years ago
- Do not know

Now we will ask you a few demographic questions. Please remember that our study is fully anonymized, and the data collection follows the GDPR principles.

Part B – Individual characteristics

6. **Age (number of years):** |__|__|

7. **Gender:**

Woman

Man

Non-binary

I prefer not to say

8. **Level of education:**

No school

Primary (elementary school)

Lower secondary (middle school)

Upper secondary (high school)

University or higher degree

9. **Country of residence:**

10. **Ethnicity**

European

North African

Middle East

Sub-saharian African

Central Asia

East and South East Asia

Pacific Islands

Caribbean -South America

Now we will ask you a few questions about any treatment you followed due to tinnitus and the out-of-pocket costs incurred over the past year. With “out-of-pocket” costs we mean the costs that were not covered or reimbursed by the National Healthcare System or by private insurance. We would like you to provide us with your most accurate estimations for how much you paid in the past 12 months.

Part C: Due to tinnitus direct medical and non-medical costs

11. Due to tinnitus, have you been in contact with any of the following healthcare providers in the past 12 months? Which was the total annual cost in local currency (You should think about the costs that were not covered or reimbursed by the National Healthcare System or by private insurance, namely “out-of-pocket costs”)? If fully covered please indicate 0. Multiple answers are possible.

Healthcare provider visited due to tinnitus in the past 12 months	Number of visits in the past 12 months	Total annual out-of-pocket costs spent by you for all the visits in the past 12 months
None	<input type="checkbox"/>	
General practitioner	_ _ _ visits	_ _ _ _ _ € spent by you for all visits to general practitioner(s) in the past 12 months
Ear, nose and throat specialist	_ _ _ visits	_ _ _ _ _ € spent by you for all visits to ear, nose and throat specialist(s) in the past 12 months
Audiologist	_ _ _ visits	_ _ _ _ _ € spent by you for all visits to audiologist(s) in the past 12 months
Psychiatrist	_ _ _ visits	_ _ _ _ _ € spent by you for all visits to psychiatrist(s) in the past 12 months
Psychologist	_ _ _ visits	_ _ _ _ _ € spent by you for all visits to psychologist(s) in the past 12 months
Chiropractor	_ _ _ visits	_ _ _ _ _ € spent by you for all visits to chiropractor(s) in the past 12 months
Physiotherapist	_ _ _ visits	_ _ _ _ _ € spent by you for all visits to physiotherapist(s) in the past 12 months

Acupuncturist	_ _ _ visits	_ _ _ _ _ € spent by you for all visits to acupuncturist(s) in the past 12 months
Homeopathist	_ _ _ visits	_ _ _ _ _ € spent by you for all visits to homeopathist(s) in the past 12 months
Osteopathist	_ _ _ visits	_ _ _ _ _ € spent by you for all visits to osteopathist(s) in the past 12 months
Other type of healthcare provider visited due to tinnitus in the past year, specify provider 1: _____	_ _ _ visits	_ _ _ _ _ € spent by you for all visits to this type of healthcare provider in the past 12 months
Other type of healthcare provider visited due to tinnitus in the past year, specify provider 2: _____	_ _ _ visits	_ _ _ _ _ € spent by you for all visits to this type of healthcare provider in the past 12 months
Other type of healthcare provider visited due to tinnitus in the past year, specify provider 3: _____	_ _ _ visits	_ _ _ _ _ € spent by you for all visits to this type of healthcare provider in the past 12 months

12. Due to tinnitus, have you received any of the below treatments in the past 12 months? Which was the total annual cost in local currency in the past 12 months (You should think about the costs that were not covered or reimbursed by the National Healthcare System or by private insurance, namely “out-of-pocket costs”)? Please be aware that you must not include costs that you already reported in the previous question. If fully covered please indicate 0. Multiple answers are possible

Treatment used due to tinnitus in the past 12 months	Total annual out-of-pocket costs spent by you for all the treatments in the past 12 months
None	<input type="checkbox"/>
Neurostimulation or Repetitive Transcranial Magnetic Stimulation (rTMS or magnet therapy)	_ _ _ _ _ € spent by you for all sessions of neurostimulation or rTMS in the past 12 months
Sound stimulation	_ _ _ _ _ € spent by you for all sessions of sound stimulation in the past 12 months

Low-Level Laser therapy	_ _ _ _ _ _ _ € spent by you for all sessions of low-level laser therapy in the past 12 months
Smartphone apps/websites for tinnitus control or management	_ _ _ _ _ _ _ € spent by you for the use of smartphone app/websites for tinnitus control or management (including fees and subscription costs) in the past 12 months
Smartphone apps/websites for relaxing	_ _ _ _ _ _ _ € spent by you for the use of smartphone app/websites for relaxing (including fees and subscription costs) in the past 12 months
Cochlear implant/Hearing aid	_ _ _ _ _ _ _ € spent by you for cochlear implants or hearing aids and/or maintenance costs if present in the past 12 months. If you have a cochlear implant or hearing aid but you did not spend money for it in the past year, not even for maintenance costs, skip this question
Masker/noise generator - a hearing aid looking device, which makes a noise	_ _ _ _ _ _ _ € spent by you for masker/noise generator - a hearing aid looking device, which makes a noise in the past 12 months. If you have a masker/noise generator but you did not spend money for it in the past year, not even for maintenance costs, skip this question

13. Due to tinnitus, have you used any of the below drugs, homeopathic preparations or dietary supplements in the past 12 months? Which was the total annual cost in local currency in the past 12 months (You should think about the costs that were not covered by the National Healthcare System or by private insurance, namely “out-of-pocket costs”)? Pharmacological drugs include, for example tranquilizers and/or anxiolytics such as alprazolam (Xanax), diazepam (Valium), anti-vertigo medication, such as betahistine (Serc), antidepressants such as Mirtazapine (Remeron). Homeopathic preparations include Bach flower remedies, Calcarea carbonica or Chininum sulfuricum. Dietary supplements include vitamins A, B complex, D, E, K, zinc, magnesium, iron. If fully covered please indicate 0. Multiple answers are possible.

Drug/homeopathic preparation/Dietary supplement taken due to tinnitus in the past 12 months	Total annual out-of-pocket costs spent by you for drug/homeopathic preparation/dietary supplement in the past 12 months
---	---

None	<input type="checkbox"/>
DRUG 1: Please specify the name: (_____)	_ _ _ _ _ _ _ € spent in the past 12 months for DRUG 1
DRUG 2: Please specify the name: (_____)	_ _ _ _ _ _ _ € spent in the past 12 months for DRUG 2
DRUG 3: Please specify the name: (_____)	_ _ _ _ _ _ _ € spent in the past 12 months for DRUG 3
DRUG 4: Please specify the name: (_____)	_ _ _ _ _ _ _ € spent in the past 12 months for DRUG 4
DRUG 5: Please specify the name: (_____)	_ _ _ _ _ _ _ € spent in the past 12 months for DRUG 5
HOMEOPATHIC PREPARATION 1: Please specify the name: (_____)	_ _ _ _ _ _ _ € spent in the past 12 months for HOMEOPATHIC PREPARATION 1
HOMEOPATHIC PREPARATION 2: Please specify the name: (_____)	_ _ _ _ _ _ _ € spent in the past 12 months for HOMEOPATHIC PREPARATION 2
HOMEOPATHIC PREPARATION 3: Please specify the name: (_____)	_ _ _ _ _ _ _ € spent in the past 12 months for HOMEOPATHIC PREPARATION 3
HOMEOPATHIC PREPARATION 4: Please specify the name: (_____)	_ _ _ _ _ _ _ € spent in the past 12 months for HOMEOPATHIC PREPARATION 4
HOMEOPATHIC PREPARATION 5: Please specify the name: (_____)	_ _ _ _ _ _ _ € spent in the past 12 months for HOMEOPATHIC PREPARATION 5
DIETARY SUPPLEMENT 1: Please specify the name: (_____)	_ _ _ _ _ _ _ € spent in the past 12 months for DIETARY SUPPLEMENT 1
DIETARY SUPPLEMENT 2: Please specify the name: (_____):	_ _ _ _ _ _ _ € spent in the past 12 months for DIETARY SUPPLEMENT 2
DIETARY SUPPLEMENT 3: Please specify the name: (_____)	_ _ _ _ _ _ _ € spent in the past 12 months for DIETARY SUPPLEMENT 3
DIETARY SUPPLEMENT 4: Please specify the name: (_____)	_ _ _ _ _ _ _ € spent in the past 12 months for DIETARY SUPPLEMENT 4

DIETARY SUPPLEMENT 5: Please specify the name: (_____)	_ _ _ _ _ € spent in the past 12 months for DIETARY SUPPLEMENT 5
OTHER 1: Please specify the name: (_____)	_ _ _ _ _ € spent in the past 12 months for OTHER 1
OTHER 2: Please specify the name: (_____)	_ _ _ _ _ € spent in the past 12 months for OTHER 2
OTHER 3: Please specify the name: (_____)	_ _ _ _ _ € spent in the past 12 months for OTHER 3

Now we will ask you few more questions to understand how tinnitus impacts your quality of life.

Part D: WTP

14. How much are you willing to pay to cure your tinnitus loudness/annoyance completely?

- Nothing
- Less than 200 euros
- 200–499 euros
- 500–999 euros
- 1,000–4,999 euros
- 5,000–9,999 euros
- 10,000–24,999 euros
- 25,000–49,999 euros
- 50,000–100,000 euros
- More than 100,000 euros

15. What part of your monthly income are you willing to pay to reduce your tinnitus loudness/annoyance by 50%?

- Nothing
- Less than 200 euros
- 200–499 euros
- 500–999 euros
- 1,000–4,999 euros
- 5,000–9,999 euros
- 10,000–24,999 euros
- 25,000–49,999 euros
- 50,000–100,000 euros
- More than 100,000 euros

For each of the upcoming questions, please select the option that best describes your health TODAY.

16. Mobility

- I have no problems in walking about
- I have slight problems in walking about
- I have moderate problems in walking about
- I have severe problems in walking about
- I am unable to walk about

17. Self-care

- I have no problems in washing or dressing myself
- I have slight problems in washing or dressing myself
- I have moderate problems in washing or dressing myself

I have severe problems in washing or dressing myself

I am unable to wash or dress myself

18. Usual activities (e.g. work, study, housework, family or leisure activities)

I have no problems doing my usual activities

I have slight problems doing my usual activities

I have moderate problems doing my usual activities

I have severe problems doing my usual activities

I am unable to do my usual activities

19. Pain/Discomfort

I have no pain or discomfort

I have slight pain or discomfort

I have moderate pain or discomfort

I have severe pain or discomfort

I have extreme pain or discomfort

20. Anxiety/Depression

I am not anxious or depressed

I am slightly anxious or depressed

I am moderately anxious or depressed

I am severely anxious or depressed

I am extremely anxious or depressed

21. We would like to know how good or bad your health is TODAY. This scale is numbered from 0 to 100. 100 means the best health you can imagine. 0 means the worst health you can imagine. Mark an X on the scale to indicate how your health is TODAY. Now, please write the number you marked on the scale in the box here: ...

Now we will ask you a few questions regarding the effect of tinnitus into your working life. We would like you to provide us with your most accurate estimations.

Part E: Indirect costs

22. Did you have any paid job within the past 12 months?

- Yes
- No

23. If yes, due to tinnitus, were you in sick leave during the past 12 months?

- Yes
- No

24. If yes, due to tinnitus, how many days in total were you on a sick leave the past 12 months?

|_|_|_| days

This was our last question, thank you for completing our questionnaire.